

**THE INTERACTIONAL ASPECT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL
DISCOURSE IN THE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING**

Raximova Go‘zal Bagriddinovna

an English teacher

The Department of Functional Lexics of English Language

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

guzal.rahimova.86@mail.ru

+998909612826

Abstract. With the independence of the Republic Uzbekistan the integration process increases the demand to the academic sphere and the requirements to the teaching foreign languages in proficiency level. In the Decree on the 19th of January in 2022, №34 “The additional measures to improve the learning of foreign languages” by the Ministry of the Republic Uzbekistan was mentioned that the deficiency in the assessment system of the education and the weakness of the qualification of the professor and teachers staff affect negatively to the quality of the education system. The teaching and training qualified pedagogical staff remain one of the main issues in the educational system of Uzbekistan. Accordingly, the study of the academic discourse is the significant issue for the improving of the pedagogical qualification and increasing the quality of the academic communication in teaching. The research paper allows us to consider the realization of the pedagogical discourse from the cognitive point of view, to understand the pragmatic peculiarities of the educational process, to reveal the cognitive -pragmatic characteristics through sociolinguistic and cross – cultural features of the communication in the foreign language teaching.

Key words: pedagogical discourse, interactional aspect, EFL classroom, maxims of speech, positive and negative face, politeness.

The features of the speech are determined by the actualization of the meanings of the particular linguistic unit in the process of the interaction. Therefore, the pedagogical

discourse can be identified as the way of the representing and the cognizing of the world in the foreign language education through speech activity aimed for the socialization of the individual. The pedagogical discourse represents an open non-linear system of the semiotic entities which are regulated by the pedagogical situation, the pedagogical goal or the intention through certain discursive strategies. There are specific stable linguistic and behavioral teacher's speech units which needed to establish contact with the audience, maintaining a conversation in the chosen key and transferring other information. They perform the regulatory function or the function of the politeness, as the result the nature of the relationship and the perception of the speech are established. In emotional and expressive approach to the process of the lesson an appeal, order, request, praise, encouragement are used. The composition of the speech is made up by various semantic blocks (semantic patterns) which are meaningfully related to each other. According to the statement of the scholar E.I. Passova, "Situations organized in the lessons, should be a unit of the communication, possess all her characteristics and recreate (model) the essential nature of the communication".¹ According to this the interaction is classified by theorists and practitioners based on types relationships such as: the situations of the social-role relations which have stereotypical, standardized character; the situations of the social relationships, where the communicants act as representatives of the social groups; the situations of the joint activity relations arising in specific forms of the activity; the situations of the moral relationships which are associated with the affective component.² Taking into account this classification, the scholar E.I. Passov and his co-authors defined the situation as the unit of the functioning of the process of the communication, existing as the integrative system of the status-role, social activity and moral relationships of the subjects of the communication.³ The communication

¹ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.: "Fan va texnologiya", 2019, 144стр.-54 стр.

² Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.: "Fan va texnologiya", 2019, 144стр.-54 стр.

³ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.: "Fan va texnologiya", 2019, 144стр.-54 стр.

strategies are also associated with the concept of “ the situation of the pedagogical communication”. Speech-thinking activity in the process of the educational process is realized through the communication strategies, which is usually understood as the plan actions to achieve the communicative goal and communicative effects realized by language means. In general, the communicative strategy correlates the goal and possible means of its achievements. In other words, the communicative strategies are algorithm of the operations and actions for the implementation of the communicative act. The repertoire of the strategies and tactics in the process of the pedagogical interaction with students is diverse and mediated by the main goal and the content of the pedagogical action - what educational information, how and in what communicative form should be conveyed to the students. In addition, there are many text generation strategies such as labeling strategies, representations, explanations, etc., which are involved in the formulation of the thought. The strategies which allow students to compensate for their gaps in language knowledge should also be called especially important. The communication strategies could be implemented by individual words or truncated sentences, fixed phrases and non-verbal signs (visibility and various paralinguistic means). Here are examples demonstrating discursive patterns teacher-student interactions. As part of the explanation material and control of its understanding, the following are used as patterns: There are lots of ways of giving advice or making recommendations. The expression you use will normally depend on the formality of the situation. Look at the table and say what means are used in the typical conversation and in the written and more formal situations. When the addresser expresses the own idea, the following phrases are used: contrasting points: but in spite of; on the one hand...., but on the other; advantages/disadvantages: first of all, the biggest disadvantage; adding points: what's more; apart from that; also. During the lesson, the teacher, as a rule, uses the following communication strategies: explaining, evaluating, controlling, facilitating, organizing. Imagine these strategies in the form of the generalizing Table 4.

Table 4. The communicative strategies in the Pedagogical discourse in EFL classroom.

The communicative strategies in the pedagogical discourse in EFL classroom	Function	Examples of speech genres
Explanatory	informative transfer of experience	Message, Explanation, Conversation Verbs: describe, name, define, present, designate, emphasize, characterize, reveal, determine, compare or give an analogy, compare, analyze, generalize or systematize, determine or specify, induce and ask, answer, interpret (interpret meanings and talk about one's own experience), abstract, reformulate, operate.
Evaluating	emotionally evaluative general evaluation and self-evaluative motivational stimulating controlling and corrective, managerial	emotional evaluative judgments like/dislike, advantages/disadvantages, good/bad, right/wrong, approval/disapproval, praise, blame, criticize, motivate, determine the

	assessment and educational	place of the object of assessment according to conditional rating scale, set ideals, determine dynamics/progression, exercise self-control and self-assessment.
Controlling	motivational stimulating controlling diagnostic corrective evaluative educational managerial educational	receive and collect information on the quality of learning and readiness to learn material; establish an objective state of affairs, diagnose shortcomings and errors, diagnose gaps and errors, determine dynamics / progression, correct, manage the educational process, produce feedback, ensure the rotation and repetition of the material, Exercise non-verbal control to motivate and intensify the activity of trainees, to produce self-contact role, test, fix, accept moral and value setting.
Interacting	organizational evaluative educational communicative	creating optimal conditions for the formation of the personality, support and correction, criticize,

		evaluate, express empathy and positive
Organizing	Joint activity teacher and learners	educate, distribute attention, respond to behavioral disturbances, establish contact (greeting, address, signs of attention), organize a successful lesson, offer a plan, give directives or instructions to allow conflicts, coordinate activities or actions to influence earners/students and achieve authority

It can be seen from the content of Table 4, the different communication strategies for the implementation of the pedagogical activities depend on the functions or roles which they perform. The communication strategies are expressed in the form of genres of the speech or speech acts. For example, the speech genre “control” is mainly realized as the acts of the understanding at all levels of the reflection. In this case, the control strategy can be defined as “feedback”. It manifests itself in checking the readiness of the student to the acquisition of the new knowledge. The teacher controls how well material learned by the student. The response supports the maintaining contact with the addressee. According to it the teacher forms the joint activity with the student: Teacher: Did all of you do the homework. Now I’m going to check it. ⁴ The interactional essence of the pedagogical discourse can also include maxims G.P. Grice as the postulates of the communicative behavior, which are directly related to the communicative activity of the teachers / lecturers of the foreign language:

⁴ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения.- Т.:”Fan va texnologiya”,2019,144стр.-56стр.

- the postulate of quantity (the communicative contribution should be more informative);
- the postulate qualities (the communicative contribution must be true - real);
- the postulate of the relevance (the communicative contribution must be relevant to the topic);
- the postulate of the manner (the communicative contribution must be clear and coherent).

Table 5. The maxims of quantity, quality and manner of the speech.

Postulates	Instructions
Quantity	make your post as informative as it gets necessary for the communication purposes
Quality	Make a message which you can bear responsibility within cultural norms.
Relevance	Make your speech connected with the topic
Manner speeches	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do not make the statement more difficult to understand. 2. Avoid ambiguity if it is not relevant to the norms of the politeness or other culturally significant values (for example respect). 3. Create statements with the length which is dictated naturally and express the purpose of the communication. 4. Structure the discourse adequately to the norms of the language culture which the communication takes place.

These instructions of the postulates are derived from the basis of all communication principle of the cooperation, namely, the postulates of quality, quantity, relation and mode of transmission of the thoughts. The non-compliance of one or more these postulates to some extent entails the communicative failure. The essence of the principle of the cooperation is the requirement which makes the communicative contribution to verbal communication in accordance with accepted purpose and direction of the conversation. However, it should pay attention to the postulates of the politeness which are not included G.P. Grice among the fundamental ones. According to the statement G.P. Grice, the task of the message is considered only as the effective transmission of the information. But in the communication the motivational speech is also the important tool. For this purpose, there are strategies for attracting attention: appeals, etiquette phrases, special comments. A sign of the attracting attention can be a change in the volume of the voice, phrasal and logical stress, work with pre-planned mistakes, etc. The politeness is one of the main communication rules. In this regard, let us dwell on the principle of the politeness, which is implemented in unison with the principle of the cooperation. The main function of the politeness in connection with the cooperation is the regulation of the social behavior of the people in the process of the communicative activity from the standpoint of the norms and conventions of behavior adopted in a particular different linguistic culture. As scientists note, the politeness is “a battery of the social skills whose goal is to ensure everyone feels affirmed in a social interaction”.⁵ This principle is based on respect for the personality of the communicator, taking into account the interests of the partner, his opinion and desires, and facilitating the tasks assigned to him. Therefore, this principle plays a special role in the process of the communication, which is in the parameters of the norms of the behavior, it is often identified with the assessment of the personal characteristics of the cultured person - delicacy, tact, decency, politeness. The principle of the politeness is realized in the process of

⁵ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.:”Fan va texnologiya”,2019,144стр.-58стр.

interaction and therefore the acts as a strategy of the speech behavior aimed at preventing possible conflict situations and implemented with the help of the various rules and tactics. The scholar S. Blum Kalka characterized the politeness as the deliberate strategic individual behavior which is directed towards satisfying one's own desires and the desires of another.⁶

There are certain politeness maxims by the scholar Geoffrey Leech.

- the maxim of tact: 'Minimize the efforts of others', 'Try increase the benefit for others';
- maxim of generosity: 'Minimize the benefit to yourself', 'Take all the effort';
- maxim of approbation: 'Do not be rude to others';
- maxim of modesty: 'Don't praise yourself', 'Praise others';
- the maxim of agreement: 'Avoid disagreements';
- maxim of sympathy: 'Be benevolent.'

These maxims also include other rules "Don't impose", "Don't force your partner", "Give him freedom choice", "Do not encroach on his rights", "Do not violate the boundaries of his personal spheres".⁷ The politeness is a relevant concept to the pedagogical discourse and it is determined by the rules adopted in the various situations of the communication which is considered polite in one communicative context may be neutral and unacceptable in another. The communicative context, which influences the choice of the form of the expression and the definition of its marking on the basis of the politeness, includes the following signs of the communicative situation: a) the mutual position of the communicants (equal, higher, lower), b) the degree of socio-psychological distances (far, close), c) the atmosphere of the communication (official, informal, not enforced). It should also be taken into account that the politeness is also associated with tonality, as the expressing of the intention by the speaker to soften the

⁶ Blum-Kalka S. Discourse Pragmatics// van Dijk T.A. (ed.) Discourse as social interaction. Discourse studies: a multidisciplinary introduction. - London: Thousand Oaks, New Delhi: SAGE Publication, 1997. Vol.2. -P.38-63.

⁷ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.: Fan va texnologiya", 2019, 144стр.-59стр.

process of communication. Therefore, the politeness is identified with speech etiquette, which is understood as a set of rules managing the communication. At the same time, the means of the expressing politeness have different values (correctness, courtesy, kindness), and the original intention is to influence the interlocutor with various verbal and non-verbal means, or by establishing contact in a polite manner. For example, in English classes the contact-establishing speech acts can be attributed by the phonetic or speech exercises: talking about the weather, doing homework, known information, etc.

In such speech acts, if there is a gap of this or that information, it replenished at the emotional-evaluative level. These speech acts perform the function of the mobilizing linguistic consciousness for the successful fulfillment of the task of the communication, and compensate for the decision making when lack of the information due to the certain emotional state. The emotional-evaluative statements are characterized by the actualization of the expressive means of the language: phonetic, morphological, lexical and syntactic. Secondly, the politeness is largely determined by the norms and conventions of the behavior reflected in the rules of etiquette, which are reduced to the system negative and positive strategies of the politeness. "Being polite means save face in front of others"⁸. Therefore, in the scientific use of pragmalinguistics and linguodidactics the concept of a face was introduced. In social interaction, the loss prevention strategies faces (face-threatening) inevitably come from the terms of the communication. A face threatening is inherently threatening to both the speaker and the listener, because the speaker is acting against the listener's expectations. Many of these strategies are verbal, but they can also be transmitted by other characteristics of speech (tone, intonation or nonverbal means). A negative face is when a person is not evades or intends to overcome an obstacle (interference) facing the freedom of the action of the interlocutor. It hurts both a speaker and listener, and makes one of the

⁸ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.: "Fan va texnologiya", 2019, 144стр.-60стр.

communicants follow someone else's will. At the same time, the freedom of choice becomes a hindrance, when there is a negative face.

Table 5. The strategies and examples of the Positive and Negative Face of the Politeness.

Face types	Speech acts
Negative face from the position listener	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an act to confirm or to deny creating pressure on the listener to submit or not to submit an act. <p>For example: orders, requests, suggestions, advice, threats and warnings.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an act which expresses the speaker's sentimentality towards listener. <p>For example: compliments, expression of envy and admiration, the expression of the strong negative emotions towards the listener (hatred, anger).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an act expressing some positive attitude towards the listener in the form of the obligation. In this case, the pressure is on the listener to accept or reject it. For example: offer, promise.
Negative face from the position speaker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the act of the concession to the listener. <p>For example: expression of gratitude: acceptance of gratitude or apology: apology; acceptance of proposals; answer to violation of the listener's social etiquette; a speaker commits himself / herself to do something, although he / she does not want to do</p>
Positive Face from the position listener	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an act expressing the negative assessment of the speaker on attitude of the listener's positive face. The speaker may show your disapproval in two ways: 1) by expressing explicitly or implicitly that he/she dislike some aspects of his possession, desires, personal representations; 2) the speaker expresses the disagreement by using

	<p>categorical words such as “you are wrong”, “it is not rational or wrong”.</p> <p>For example: the expression of the disapproval (resentment, insult, accusation, complaint), contradiction, disagreement, problems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the act of the expressing indifference to the speakers towards the positive face of the listener. • the listener may find it difficult or afraid to answer. <p>For example: extremely emotional expressions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The speaker emphasizes the dissimilarity of the value orientations or fears with the listener. <p>For example: disrespect, mentioning a topic which is inappropriate in general or to the subject of the speech.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the speaker emphasizes that his desire is being ignored by listener emotionally. <p>For example: underestimating, neglect, boasting.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the speaker reinforces the possibility of the face threatening. This situation is created when the speaker talks about the subject, relating to social sensitivity. <p>For example: topics related to politics, religion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the speaker notes that he perceives the listener's positive face differently. This is often the case when the obvious non-cooperative behavior. <p>For example: interruption, illogicality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the speaker is not aware of an offensive and challenging tone and does not take into account the status, age or gender of the communication partner. For example: appeal, arrogance
Positive face	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the act of the demonstrating which the speaker is in some way wrong and unable to control himself.

<p>from the position speaker</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • apology: In this act, the speaker in the position face-threatening, agreeing to the negation of one disagreement of previous acts. • accepting a compliment • inability to control someone • inability to control your emotions • self-abasement, admission of guilt, mistakes.
----------------------------------	---

According to the studies of the scholar S. Blum-Kulka and T.V. Elizarova the positive face of the politeness is the anxiety of the person that the others think well of her / him as making a positive contribution to public order, and the negative face of the politeness reserves to the person the right of non-intervention in his/her affairs.⁹ The scholar G.V. Elizarova refers to the strategies of the positive face politeness the following: attention to the listener, underlining mutually acceptable positions, the formulation of common points of view, the demonstration of the optimism. And the listener's strategies for preserving the speaker's face is interpreted by the author as giving him/her the right not to perform an action, demonstrating pessimistic attitude, the usage a set of the introductory expressions, such as: I wonder if., I only want to know..., You might consider doing.... The researcher also noted some examples in English culture which are full in accordance with the values of the freedom and autonomy of the individual, own responsibility for everything which happens and a small distance in the parameter of the power. As proof for the stated statement the author gave the following examples: When students are late in an English-speaking society, there may be phrase used: I was beginning to worry that something had happen to you. Uzbek nation does not recognize the cultural meaning of this phrase and therefore do not regard it as a reproach. Or another situation: You might consider reading some more about the subject. (You could read more about it). It might be

⁹ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.:” Fan va texnologiya”,2019,144стр.-61стр.

helpful if you try one more option (It would be nice if you tried to use more one approach, one more tries. – Opportunity). Such expressions are perceived by Uzbek students not as value judgments containing recommendations and requirements, but as personal wishes of the professor, they can be considered optional. Additionally, to the element of the politeness, containing in its structure strategies for the preventing and mitigating interactional conflicts can be attributed to mitigation (mitigation - lat. mitigate - soften, loosen). The main content of the mitigation are strategies softening intentionality aimed at minimizing all sorts of undesirable effects in a speech act.¹⁰ In addition, such a component of the politeness is associated with tolerance and emotive empathy. In other words, the speaker in the process of the verbalization, for example, he wants his request to be fulfilled and he uses various strategies of illocutionary influence on the interlocutor and softening his request. In other words, it will occur communicative rule- soften the intensity of the manifestation of the emotions in communication; soften the harshness of the statement and make it less straightforward. This component includes prescriptions, settings, rules, guided by which the speaker chooses the most optimal strategies or tactics for realizing your intention, corresponding to the background expectations of the listener and uses evasion strategy in the form of a set of structures - softening devices. Mitigation is one of the important conditions in the pedagogical discourse in the polite communication with students. In order not to offend the feelings of students/pupils by expressing opinion or criticism, or expressing attitude and advice, do not sound too categorically and was not perceived as too instructive, it is necessary to form your speech in a polite form. In this regard, the article by I.V. Pevneva experimentally proved the success of the using those or other communicative strategies to overcome the conflict situation in the pedagogical discourse. The researcher demonstrated the following communication strategies undertaken by the professor in relation to the obtained grades and the students in response to his comments: 1) cooperation and mitigation from the position of the

¹⁰ Махкамова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.:” Fan va texnologiya”,2019,144стр.-62стр.

professor: Ok, what exactly you don't understand. Stay after classes and I will help you. Do you have some extra time, we can go over what you don't understand. Phrases which provoke conflicts by the professor: Read it over again and come to me. I am afraid you didn't reach your full potential. 2) cooperation and mitigation from the position of students: Could you please explain the reasons for this grade so I could improve. If that's what I deserve, that's ok. Well ok then. Is there any way I can redo this paper? Phrases which provoke further development of the conflict from the position students: It is not your business. I am paying to this class. Taking everything into account, it can be considered that it is necessary to research the communicative interaction for the revealing pragmatic features of the pedagogical discourse.

The analysis of the pedagogical discourse shows the complexity of the pedagogical discourse, because the pedagogical discourse realizes the peculiarities of the perception and understanding in the educational process. The pedagogical discourse contributes the evaluation of the cultural activity and obtaining the experience with the socio –cultural norms in the education process. The essential assumption of the pedagogical discourse is to transfer the knowledge which is connected with human being and history. The pedagogical discourse is as the institutional discourse is created in the certain template, which the purpose of the communication determines by the theme and tonality of the discourse. According to the statement of V. Bernstein the pedagogical discourse is the special institutional methods of the expressing and comprehending of the world picture in the educational process. The pedagogical discourse includes all pedagogical activities. The different communication strategies for the implementation of the pedagogical activities depend on the functions or roles which they perform. The communication strategies are expressed in the form of genres of the speech or speech acts. The revealed features of the interactional aspect of the pedagogical discourse in foreign language teaching can contribute the improvement to the quality of the education process and to increase the effective learning, to help the minimizing of the communicative failures in the education process.

THE USED LITERATURE

1. Ashurova D.U, Galiyeva M.R. Text Linguistics-Coursebook for Master students in specialty Linguistics English language.- Tashkent., Turon-Iqbol, 2016.-324 p.
2. Ashurova D.U. Galieva M.R. Cognitive Linguistics – Tashkent: VneshInvestProm, 2018.-160p.
3. Bardovi-Harlig K. Pragmatics and second language acquisition. // In Kaplan R. (ed.). Handbook of Applied Linguistics. -OUP, 2002. -Pp. 182- 192
4. Bernstein B. Class, Codes and Control 4: The Structuring of Pedagogic Discourse. - Routledge, London, 1990.
5. Bernstein B. Pedagogy, Symbolic Control and Identity: theory, research, critique. — Taylor & Francis, London, 2000.
6. Berry M. Systemic Linguistics and Discourse Analysis: A MultiLayered Approach to Exchange Structure. //In Studies in Discourse Analysis. Ed. by M. Coulter & M. Montgomery. - London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1981. - Pp. 120-145.
7. Blum-Kalka S. Discourse Pragmatics// van Dijk T.A. (ed.) Discourse as social interaction. Discourse studies: a multidisciplinary introduction. - London: Thousand Oaks, New Delhi: SAGE Publication, 1997. Vol. 2. - Pp. 38-63
8. Blum-Kalka S., House J., Kasper G. (eds.). Cross-cultural Pragmatics. - Ablex, Norwood, NJ, 1989.
9. Boxer D. & Pickering L. Problems in the presentation of speech acts in ELT materials: The case complaints. // ELT Journal. 1995, 49. -Pp. 44-58.
10. Boxer D. Critical issues in development pragmatics. // In Martinez-Flor A., Uso-Juan E., Fernandez-Guerra A. (eds.) Pragmatic competence in Foreign Language Teaching. — Servei de Publicacions Universitat Jaume I., Castello, 2003. - Pp.45-67.
11. Brown P. & Levinson S. Politeness: Some Universals in Language Use. - Cambridge: CUP, 1987.

12. Brown P. & Yule G. Teaching the Spoken Language. - Cambridge: CUP, 1983.
13. Celce-Murcia M. Rethinking the Role of Communicative Competence in Language Teaching. // In book: Intercultural Language Use and Language Learning. E. Alcon Soler, M.P. Safont Jorda (eds). - Springer, 2007. - Pp. 41-57.
14. Celce-Murcia M., Domyei Z. & Thurrell S. Communicative competence: A pedagogically motivated framework with content specifications. // Issues in Applied Linguistics. 1995, 6. -Pp. 5-35.
15. Chomsky N. Aspects of the theory of syntax. -Cambridge: MIT Press, 1965.
16. Christie F. Classroom Discourse Analysis. - Continuum, London, 2002.
17. Cristie F. & Maton K. Disciplinarity: Functional linguistic and sociological perspective. -London: Continuum, 2011.
18. Cristiee F. & Martin R. (Eds.) Language. Knowledge and Pedagogy: Functional Linguistic and Sociological Perspectives. - London: Cassells, 2007.
19. Dhieb-Henia N. Applying Metacognitive Strategies to Skimming Research Articles in an ESP Context. // English Teaching Forum Journal.V.44, No 1.2006. - Pp.2-7.
20. Dijk T.A. The study of discourse. // T.A. van Dijk (ed.) Discourse as structure and process. Discourse studies: A multidisciplinary introduction. V.1. - London, New Delhi, 1997.
21. Dijk T.A. "Discourse as structure and Process". London 1997.
22. Обдалова О.А. Когнитивно-Дискурсивная система обучения иноязычной межкультурной коммуникации студентов бакалавриата естественнонаучных направлений. /Диссертация на соискание ученой степени доктора педагогических наук. /Нижний Новгород – 2017.468стр.
23. Алиференко Н.Ф. Лингвокультурология. Ценностно-смысловое пространство языка: Учебное пособие. -М. Флинта. Наука, 2010. - 224 с.

24. Богатырева.О.П. Функционально-семантическая характеристика учебного языкового текста на материале английского языка: дис. канд. филол. наук: 10.02.04 /– Тверь, 2006. – 237 стр.
25. Ежова Т.В. К проблеме изучения педагогического дискурса. // Вестник Оренбургского государственного университета. 2006, №2. Том 1: Гуманитарные науки. - С. 52-56.
26. Жалолов Ж.Ж. Сайланма: илмий мақолалар тўплами. – Тошкент: ТДПУ, 2017. – 318 б.
27. Казанцова Е.А. Лингвоэкологический и когнитивно – прагматический характеристики академического дискурса в англоязычных и русский лингвокультурах: дис. канд. филол. наук: 10.02.20/ Уфа, 2020. -495с.
28. Карасик В.И. Языковой круг: личность, концепты, дискурс. - Волгоград, 2002. -477 с.
29. Маслова В.А. Введение в когнитивную лингвистику. - М.: ФлинтаНаука, 2008. -296 с.
30. Махаммова Г.Т. Педагогический дискурс иноязычного образования: проблемы и решения. - Т.: “Fan va texnologiya” ,2019.-144стр.
31. Махаммова Г.Т. Концепция формирования межкультурной компетенции студентов факультетов английского языка: Монография. - Ташкент: «Фан» Академии Наук Республики Узбекистан, 2010. -207 с.
32. Махаммова Г.Т. Формирование межкультурной компетенции студентов филологического вуза (английский язык): Дис. д.п.н. —Т.: УзГУМЯ. 2011.-335 с.
33. Мухаммад Х.И.А. Прагматический компонент Взаимодействие в аудиторном дискурсе на материале речи преподавателя. /Дис.на соискание ученой степени кан. Филологических наук. Москва. 2006.-280 стр.
34. Пассов Е.И., Киберева Л.В., Колларова Э. Концепция коммуникативного иноязычного образования (Теория и ее реализация): Методическое пособие для русистов. -СПб.: Златоуст, 2007. —200 с.

35. Савельева И.Ф. Формирование знаниевого компонента лингвосоциокультурной компетенции. // В кн.: Современная методика соизучения иностранных языков и культур. - СПб.: Каро, 2011.
36. Сафаров Ш. Прагмалингвистика – Монография, Тошкент, 2008. – 318б.
37. Сусов И. П. Семантика и прагматика предложения. - Капинин, 1980.- 150 с.
38. Танчук А.С. Дискурсивные характеристики англоязычных вебинаров по обучению английскому языку. /Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Самара. 2021.-205 стр.
39. Тленкопачева М. Н. Основные элементы педагогического дискурса // Актуальные вопросы филологических наук: Материалы III Междунар. науч. конф. Казань: Бук, 2015. 57-60 стр.
40. Толочко О. В. Образ как составляющая концепта «школа» // Языковая личность: проблемы лингвокультурологии и функциональной семантики. -Волгоград: Перемена, 1999.
41. Трепак Я. В. Лингвостилистические и когнитивно-прагматические характеристики дискурса академической блогосферы. / Дис.на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук. Москва 2016. -226стр.
42. Чудинов А.П. Прагматический потенциал метафоры в педагогической коммуникации// Педагогическое образование в России. – Екатеринбург. 2011. №5.